

ORGANIZATION OF CLASSES ON THE TOPIC OF QUALITY IN THE 3RD GRADE BASED ON NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article describes the methodical basis of using problem-based educational technologies in the teaching of the topic "Adjective Vocabulary" of Mother Language Science in the course of modern education. This article serves as a resource for use in the mother tongue classes of secondary schools.

Key words: pedagogy, education, primary class, educational technologies.

Introduction: The scope of new pedagogical knowledge is expanding based on the requirements of the Law "On Education", research directions are focused on the problems of free personality formation. Today, effective use of various teaching methods is important in the educational process. When native language classes are organized on the basis of innovative technology, the students develop the ability to work cooperatively, they help each other in finding solutions to common tasks, the students develop creative and independent thinking skills, and the students develop their own they feel personally responsible for the result of their work, study, and education. Currently, problem-based teaching technology is effective in any educational institution. Its task is to encourage the process of active cognition and to form a scientific-research method in thinking, which corresponds to the goals of creative, active personality education. The essence of problem-based teaching is the teacher's management of students' cognitive activities to acquire new knowledge by creating a problem situation in their educational work and solving educational tasks, problems and questions. Signs of a problematic situation are as follows: - presence of an unfamiliar fact in the student: - the instructions given to the student to complete the tasks, their personal interest in solving the cognitive difficulties that have arisen. Being able to get out of a problematic situation is always connected with the understanding of the problem, that is, what is unknown, its verbal expression and solution. If we analyze the problem situation intellectually, it is, first of all, the independent mental activity of students. It leads the student to understand the reasons that caused intellectual difficulty, to enter it, to express the problem in words, that is, to define active thinking. Here the consistency is clear: first, a problem situation arises, then a learning problem is formed. There are also important signs of a learning problem in the teaching process. Important signs of the learning problem are: - addition of the unknown, which leads to the formation of new knowledge; - students have a certain knowledge reserve necessary to carry out research in order to find the unknown.

Analysis of the result: In order for the student to be able to think in the situation he wants, to answer any question correctly, to be able to think correctly, during the lesson, their various technological, that is, the development of the expansion of the children's mind Through ideas, i.e., projects, lessons are organized and children are developed, and various simple and complex concepts are given to them. In primary grades, the system of studying the adjective

series envisages consistently enriching and complicating the learning material from the lexical and grammatical aspects. Students learn the lexical and grammatical meanings of adjectives and adjectives from the period of literacy training up to the 4th grade in the scope of the primary-grade native language program. During the period of literacy training, the meaning of the words indicated by the teacher, "What does an apple taste like?" What color is an apple? What size is an apple?" they learn practically by observing based on questions like In grades 1 and 2, students are taught what quality is and use a variety of learning materials to make it interesting, teach them what quality is, and explain what quality is. goes, that is, what is the quality, what is the answer to the questions and examples are given to keep it in mind. For example, a red apple, in this, that is, in this word, what is the answer to the question of quality, what kind of apple? it is called a red apple, then the adjective expresses the redness of the apple. By giving many similar examples, the children repeat in their minds the answer to the word "what quality" until it is memorized, that is, until it reaches this level, and they retain it, and the teacher gave an example, and now the student should be edited. That is, what kind of teacher says, the girl in the red cap; here he asks what word is the quality Students ask questions to each word, that is, what is red, what is a hat, who is a girl, because red is an adjective here, because it is an answer to the question. In this way, the ability to retain the student through questions and answers begins to develop. In this case, the important task before the teacher is to make students understand that the signs of things and people are different, that is, things differ according to their color, taste, shape, smell, size, and characteristics, and that these are the signs of things and people. , by using them effectively in the speech, enriching the students' speech with sign words and growing their speech. In particular, it is necessary to attach great importance to the exercises on describing things and people according to their signs and to the educational tasks related to this. In the 3rd and 4th grades, after being introduced to the term quality, they will have elementary theoretical information about this term. In the 3rd-4th grade, based on the knowledge and skills of students about the specific lexical-grammatical features of adjectives, oral and written creative works - organizing a trip to a school garden or a park, where a tree was observed, Describing birds and animals and creating a small story is given a special place. In order to successfully implement this, it is advisable to organize lexical-semantic and grammatical exercises to observe the use of synonyms and antonyms, adjectives in their own and figurative meanings, and to create adjectives in the native language and reading classes. In native language and reading lessons, students' speech is enriched with new adjectives, the meaning of adjectives known to them in advance is clarified. Adjectives serve to enrich children's speech and imagination. Adjectives allow to clearly describe and express things and events. Using this opportunity, teaching to compose a creative text will clarify students' thoughts and increase the effectiveness of their speech.

Conclusion: the program of primary grades does not specifically introduce students to the division of word groups into independent and auxiliary word groups, but the teacher practically introduces children to the signs of word groups. The main task in learning vocabulary is to develop students' oral and written speech, to enrich their vocabulary with new nouns, adjectives, numbers, and verbs, to ensure that students clearly understand the meaning of the words they have been using until now, to develop the skills of using one or another word appropriately in connected speech. . In order to successfully solve these tasks, synonyms and antonyms are regularly studied in the process of learning vocabulary, students

are introduced to ambiguous words and their literal and figurative use. It is important to connect education with the personal experiences of students, what they have seen directly, what they have heard on the radio, and what they have learned from books. Vocabulary learning occupies a large and important place in the education of the mother tongue of the primary grade. In the process of studying word groups, students' vocabulary is increased. They master the norms of literary and orthoepic pronunciation, spelling literacy is formed. Oral and written communication skills develop. They will have the opportunity to understand the thoughts of others, to assimilate what they read, to convey their thoughts to others, to the listener, in a free and understandable manner. It is not difficult to understand the need to develop effective methods and means of teaching it if we consider the practical importance of teaching vocabulary in primary classes. In particular, teaching students to use the materials of artistic works to study the subject in the mother tongue classes also gives its effective results. Taking this into account, integration of reading lessons with the mother tongue lesson in learning the complex grammatical features of noun and adjective word groups in 4th grade also gives effective results. In the process of studying the subject of "horse", it is necessary to make effective use of texts that cover all its features.

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